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ROLE OF SENSEX & MFI ON INVESTMENT DECISIONS OF FII IN INDIA

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ABSTRACT

There are many factors that affect the investment decisions of foreign institutional investors in India. Movement of market indices e.g. Sensex and investment behavior of mutual funds are two important factors that fall in this domain. This research paper is an attempt to analyze the impact of these factors i.e. Sensex and mutual funds on the investment decisions of Foreign Institutional Investors in India. In other word, this study explores whether the movement of two capital market indicators Sensex and Mutual Fund investments affect the investment decisions of Foreign Institutional Investors in India or not. For this purpose the authors have used regression analysis. Very interestingly, the study reveals that Sensex movement does affect the investment decisions of FIIs in India whereas the FIIs do not bother much about mutual funds.

Foreign Institutional Investors (FIIs) play a very important role in Indian stock market. The FIIs bring liquidity, buoyancy and growth in stock markets but at the same time they also inject germs of volatility and instability. Over past few years the stock markets in India have shown an impressive growth. The stock market indices are reaching new heights every day and more and more number of shares is making new highs. Reflecting India's improving macroeconomic fundamentals, increasing corporate profitability and competitiveness, and greater integration with the world economy, the Foreign Institutional Investors' (FIIs) participation is continuously increasing in the stock markets of India. In fact, the investments by FIIs in Indian stock markets are growing at a rapid rate.

1. Introduction

Indian economy faced the balance of payment crisis in 1990-91 because of which government of India introduced the liberalization policy in 1991-92. During this era, for the first time FIIs were permitted to invest in all the listed securities of Indian capital market on 14th September 1992 to reduce country's dependence on debt-creating capital flows, correct the balance of payment position and develop the capital and security. Along with that, it introduced large number of policy changes in India to integrate domestic financial and global markets which permits free flow of capital flows from developed to developing economies, resulting into higher rate of return, increased productivity and capital efficiency at global level (Chakraborty 2007; Bekaert & Harvey, 2000).

Foreign capital plays a significant role in the development of every national economy (Goudarzi & Ramanarayanan, 2011). Apart from foreign investment, domestic investment also contributes for the growth and development of capital market of the country. There are two major categories of institutional investors in Indian financial market namely Foreign Institutional Investors and Mutual Funds. FII net investments have been positive every year except 1998-99, 2007-08 and 2008-09. Country has received large amount of FII flows after

2003 (SEBI (a)). At the end of March 2013, FIIs' cumulative net investment has reached \$171618.5 million as compared to \$15939.4 million in March 2003 (SEBI (a)). At the end of March 2013, mutual funds' net Investment resulted into an inflow of Rs. 141184 crore in comparison to Rs. 68366.2 crore through FII investments (SEBI (b)). At the end of same quarter, the number of FIIs registered with SEBI has increased to 1757.

Figure 1 depicts the relationship of investment by FIIs, MFs and Sensex in Indian capital market. It shows the increasing trends from 2005-06 to 2007-08. But in 2008-09, market has gone negative with the outflow of domestic and foreign investors. It has affected the movement of stock market returns due to the global meltdown in economy of world with the emergence of sub-prime crisis in 2008. Indian economy indirectly touched the heat of the global repercussion which has impacted the reserves position of the country.

Source: Constructed in Excel through data compiled from SEBI and BSE

Figure 1: Relationship between Investments by FIIs, Investment by MFs and Sensex

Stock market returns are determined by the combination of domestic as well as foreign investments. Domestic or local investors seize greater knowledge about Indian financial markets than that of foreign investors who belongs to some other country (Chakraborty, 2007). Over the last few years, FIIs and MFs both have contributed in the subsequent increase in the stock prices of Indian capital market (Mukherjee & Roy, 2011). Every investor has a similar objective of investment such as, maximum returns, risk exposure, favorable economic and liquidity condition of the investing country (Anuradha & Rajendran, 2012). Stock market provides investors with large number of scrips with varying degree of risk, return and liquidity.

However, the economic policies of the country worldwide decreased the burden of government regulations which emphasized the inflow of foreign capital into the country (Mudambi, Navarra, & Delios, 2013). In the capital market, there are a wide range of options among the investors whether domestic or foreign investors in terms of assets. These options have increased competition, enhanced risk elements as well as the Gross Domestic Products (GDP) of the country, which ultimately leads to the movement of Sensitivity Index of the stock market (Goudarzi & Ramanarayanan, 2011).

This paper attempts to analyze the Impact of Sensex and mutual fund investments on investment decisions of FIIs in India. The rest of the paper proceeds as follows: section two deals with the review of literature, while section three talks about objectives of this study. Section four entails database and methodology, describing the nature of data and sources from which relevant data has been collected, the tools and techniques employed in the study, followed with the analysis of results in section five. Lastly, Section six deals with findings and conclusion.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Determinants and Implications of FIIs in Indian Stock Market

The term FIIs has been conceptually and empirically explained by various researchers to illustrate its effectiveness in the Indian capital market. Rao, Murthy, & Ranganathan (1999) observed that only few FIIs are active on the Indian stock market. They further observed that US-based India specific funds suggested a close resemblance between FII investment profile and trading pattern at the BSE. Chakraborty (2007) detected the direction of causality between FII flows and Indian stock market returns and described that the causality between FII flows and stock returns are highly model specific. However, Srikanth & Kishore (2012) observed that there was bi-directional causality between net FII inflows and the Sensex which mutually reinforced each other.

Bose (2012) explored the interaction between the investment flows of FIIs and MFs of the post crisis period from April 1, 2008 to March 31, 2012 on daily basis. The author found strong negative relationship between them. Domestic MFs determined their investment flows on the basis of their own previous investments, FII investments and market returns.

Prasanna (2008) highlighted about the contribution of FIIs particularly among the companies in the sensitivity index of the BSE. He also examined the relationship between FIIs' investment and firm specific characteristics in terms of ownership structure, financial performance and stock performance. They pointed out that foreign investments are more in companies which have high volume of publicly held shares. They further found that in financial performance variables, share returns and earnings per share are more influencing variables on the investment decision. However, Gupta (2011) provided evidence which shows that Indian Stock Market and FIIs both influence each other but their timing of influence is different.

Sehgal & Tripathi (2009a) concluded that both the domestic foreign institutional investors (DFIIs) or MFs and FIIs follow a positive feedback trading mechanism chasing stock market returns and FIIs seem to be reacting faster compared to DFIIs in the case of the equity market. Saha (2009) found that Indian market offers reasonable safe returns in the emerging market space. Bansal & Pasricha (2009) explained that there is no significant change in the Indian stock market average returns after the opening up of the stock market for the FIIs. According to Bohra & Dutt (2011) the behavior of FII in last decade was opportunistic whereas Profit accumulation was prime objective behind the portfolio investments in India.

Shareholding pattern of the BSE Sensex companies affected the ups and downs of Sensex. To through a light on this Tripathi (2008) analyzed the impact of FII investments on the shareholding pattern of BSE Sensex companies along with the magnitude of change in the share of various shareholders. The author found that the FII flows in the BSE Sensex companies is about 34% of the total outstanding share, which is not significant as compared to the size of capital market. Dhamija (2008) and Kaur & Dhillon (2010) observed that firm-level characteristics and macroeconomic-level conditions influencing FII investment and Sensex has considered as one of the important macro factor which influence market return.

Mukherjee & Roy (2011) compared the nature and determinants of MF decisions to that of the FIIs. The author found that MFs influence the decision of FIIs when they invest in equity and FIIs do exactly opposite to what MFs do. MFs are more cautious when they invest in debt compared to equity. Jain, Meena, & Mathur (2012) observed that FIIs are influencing the Sensex movement to a greater extent. Sensex has increased when there are positive inflows of FIIs and vice-versa. Siddiqui & Azad (2012) found that FIIs have a significant influence on the Indian financial market indices. Loomba (2012) provided the evidence of significant positive correlation between FII activity and effects on Indian Capital Market.

Dasgupta (2012) aimed to investigate the impact of and relationship between FII and MF net flows in Indian stock market from April 2007 to March 2012 using monthly data. The study found no short term as well as long term relationship between them.

Hence, most of the researchers (Rao, Murthy, & Ranganathan, 1999; Chakraborty, 2007; Kumar, N.A; Saha, 2009; Bansal & Pasricha, 2009; Gupta, 2011; Srikanth & Kishore, 2012 Loomba, 2012) have given their emphasis about its relation with Indian stock market along with the amount of volatility to be involved in it. There are rich literature in which Micro economic variables and Firm level characteristics are considered to be important determinants of FII Investment (Rao, Murthy, & Ranganathan, 1999; Prasanna, 2008; Tripathi, 2008; Dhamija 2008; Saha, 2009; Bansal & Pasricha, 2009; Kaur & Dhillon, 2010; Lakshmi, 2011; Bohra & Dutt, 2011; Mukherjee & Roy, 2011; Jain, Meena, & Mathur, 2012; Siddiqui & Azad, 2012; Anuradha & Rajendran, 2012; Srikanth & Kishore, 2012).

Huge literature have been found that defines the cause and effect relationship between variables by employing Granger Causality Test (Chakraborty, 2007; Sehgal & Tripathi, 2009a; Ray, 2009; Sehgal & Tripathi, 2009b; Mishra, Das, & Pradhan, 2010; Mukherjee & Roy, 2011; Srikanth & Kishore, 2012).

2.2 Determinants and Implications of FIIs in Global Stock Market

The significance of FII flows has been observed all over the world. Various researchers have provided an evidence regarding the importance of FIIs in Global Stock Markets. The researchers particularly Aggarwal, Klapper, & Wysocki (2005); Chen, Wang, & Lin (2008); Ting, Yen, & Chiu (2008); Burnie & Ridder (2009); Kim, Sul, & Kang (2010); Lee & Fang (2011); Bredin & Liu (2011); Boubakri, Hamza, & Kooli (2011); Abdioglu, Khurshed, & Stathopoulos (2012) have observed about the market behavior of US, Taiwan, China, Sweden and Korea market.

Aggarwal, Klapper, & Wysocki (2005) examined that at the country level, US Mutual funds invest more in open emerging markets with stronger accounting standards, shareholder rights, and legal frameworks. At the firm level, US funds are found to invest more in firms that adopt discretionary policies such as greater accounting transparency and the issuance of an ADR. Stepanyan (2011) examined the role of institutional investors in accelerating the development of capital markets and economies abroad, the determinants of their investment, both in the domestic and foreign markets. Abdioglu, Khurshed, & Stathopoulos (2012) observed the investment preferences of foreign institutional investors investing in the U.S. market. The study analyzed both firm and country-level determinants that influence the foreign Institutional investors' allocation choices.

However, In the Global context the researchers have given more emphasis to Corporate Governance Practices (Chen, Wang, & Lin, 2008; Kim, Sul, & Kang, 2010; Bredin & Liu, 2011; Stepanyan, 2011; Abdioglu, Khurshed, & Stathopoulos, 2012) which is an important determinant attracting more FII inflows into the stock market.

Hence, In the prior research, most of the focus has been emphasized on establishing the relationship between FIIs and stock market return, corporate governance practices, firm and country level determinants but less attention has been given to establish relationship of

FII's with domestic financial market variables especially MF's and Sensex especially for the duration of 2005-06 to 2012-13 on quarterly basis.

1. Objectives of Study

The present study aims to find out:

- 3.1 The impact of investment by MF's on investment decisions of FII's in India.
- 3.2 The impact of the movement of Sensex on investment decisions of FII's in India.

4. Research Methodology

4.1 Sample of the Study and Data Collection

The present study is secondary in nature and consists of the three variables namely FII investments, Sensex and MF Investments. FII and MF Investments comprises the net investment which is a difference between gross purchase and Sales. The required data related to FII Investments, Sensex and MF Investments has been collected from the various sources via websites of BSE and SEBI. Sensex data have been collected from the reports and archives of the BSE whereas data of FII Investment and MF Investment has been collected from the official website of SEBI. For all the three variables abbreviations specifically FNI (FII net investment), SnX (Sensex) and MFI (MF net investment) have been used for the data analysis. The sample period for the study spans from financial year 2005-06 to 2012-13 on quarterly basis. This period is highly significant as during this duration Indian economy has seen the stability as well as instability in the financial market due to emergence of sub-prime crisis in 2008 and eurozone crisis in late 2009. This has resulted into an outflow of foreign capital from the country which has affected the reserves positions of an economy.

4.2 Statistical Tools & Techniques

Data has been analyzed by applying the statistical tools such as correlation and regression analysis to address the objective of the study. Correlation coefficient is statistical tool that measures the strength and degree of association between two variables. Its value ranges from -1 to +1 which indicates about the positive and negative correlation between variables (Hair, Black, Babin, & Anderson, 2013). On the other hand, the regression analysis is a statistical technique used to evaluate the impact of two or more independent variables on single dependent variable.

4.3 Model / Hypothesis Framing

To test the impact of SnX and MFI on FNI, one model is framed which depicts SnX and MFI as independent variables and FNI as dependent variable. The hypotheses behind the model are:

- H0a** SnX does not affect the investment decisions of FII's in India.
- H1a** SnX affects the investment decisions of FII's in India.
- H0b** MFI does not affect the investment decisions of FII's in India.
- H1b** MFI affects the investment decisions of FII's in India.

To test the above hypotheses the equation behind the model is expressed below:

$$FNI_t = C + aSnX + bMFI + e$$

Where,

- FNI_t = FII Investment in the given period t
- C = Constant
- SnX = Sensex
- MFI = MF Investment
- e = Error term

5. Data Analysis

5.1 Correlation Matrix

The correlation coefficients in Table 1 offer bivariate relationship among all the variables FNI, SnX and MFI respectively. The first column of table shows the inter correlation between

all the dependent and independent variables. As per the result, all the predictors/Independent variables (SnX and MFI) are positively correlated with criterion (FNI) variable, in which SnX (.630) has moderate degree and MFI (.440) has low degree of positive correlation with FNI. These correlations are found to be significant at 0.1%, 1% and 5% Significance level.

	FNI	SnX	MFI
FNI	1.000		
SnX	.630***	1.000	
MFI	.440*	.561**	1.000

Note: *** p<.001, **p<.01, *p<.05

5.2 Regression Analysis

Model Summary Table 2 describes about the acceptability of the model. To check the validation of the model, the table deals with R value, R-square, adjusted R-square and Durbin and Watson value. R represents the multiple correlation coefficients, shows the linear correlation among all the variables. Higher the value of R, strong will be the relationship between the predictors (SnX and MFI) and criterion variable (FNI). In this study R, by using all the predictors simultaneously is .639, indicating that the correlation among the predictors are moderately impressive. R-Square is a squared value of multiple correlation coefficients. Higher the value of R-square higher will be the explanatory power of the model (Hair, Black, Babin, & Anderson, 2013). The value of R-Square is 0.408 which indicates that 40.8% of the variance in FNI can be predicted through SnX and MFI. The adjusted R square should ideally be equal or close to the value of R square (Ghosh, Satyawadi, Joshi, Ranjan, & Singh, 2012). In the Table II the value of adjusted R square is 0.367 which is close to the value of R square, indicates the fitness of the model. The value of Durbin-Watson should be closed to 2 for the better prediction of an assumption. In the table 2, it is 1.469 which is quite close to 2 indicating about the better estimate of model.

Model	R	R-Square	Adjusted R-Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.639	.408	.367	19315.88057	1.469

Note: Predictors (Constant), SnX, MFI
Dependent Variable: FNI

The ANOVA Table 3 evaluated the acceptability of the model on a statistical basis. The Regression row indicates information about the variation i.e. accounted by the model and the Residual row displays information about the variation that has not been accounted by the model (Sultana & Pardhasaradhi, 2012). The table shows that the combination of predictors significantly predict the dependent variable or not. The value of F=9.993 at P<0.001 indicates about the acceptability of significance level.

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1. Regression	7.457E9	2	3.729E9	9.993	.000
Residual	1.082E10	29	3.731E8		
Total	1.828E10	31			

Note: Predictors (Constant), SnX, MFI
Dependent Variable: FNI

5.3 Test for Coefficients and Co-linearity

Table 4 indicates the coefficients and co-linearity between variables when multiple regression analysis is applied. The Tolerance and VIF are two co-linearity statistics. Value of VIF should be less than 10, and tolerance should be less than 0.2. In this model, both the values are lower than their standard value hence there is no problem of co-linearity among the variables used in the model and multiple regression analysis is appropriate.

On the other hand, Beta coefficient reflects the change in the dependent variable for each unit change in the independent variable (Hair, Black, Babin, & Anderson, 2013). It can be used to compare the relative strength of various predictors within the model. Larger will be the beta coefficient, smaller will be the significance level. As per the Table IV, SnX (Beta=.559, $p < .01$) has largest beta coefficient which is statistically significant at 1% significance level. While, MFI (Beta=.126) has smaller beta coefficient which is not statistically significant.

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	Co-linearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1 (Constant)	- 37586.888	14957.650		-2.513	.018		
SnX		1.099	.559	3.241*	.003	.685	1.459
MFI	3.561 .077	.105	.126	.731	.471	.685	1.459
Note: Dependent Variable: FNI * $p < 0.01$							

5.4 Hypothesis Testing

The p-value of SnX shown in Table 4 is .003 which is less than 0.01 on the other hand; the p-value of MFI is .471 which is more than 0.05. Thus the null hypothesis H0a has been rejected, whereas H0b has been accepted. Hence it is concluded that SnX affects the investment decisions of FIIs in India whereas they do not bother about investments by MFs.

6. Finding and Conclusion

On the basis of above study, it is concluded that the null hypothesis H0a has been rejected (i.e. H1a has been accepted) whereas H0b has been accepted (i.e. H1b has been rejected), which means that Sensex affects the investment decisions of FIIs in India whereas they don't bother about MFs.

Investment in Indian Capital Market is a combination of Foreign as well as domestic investments in which MFs and FIIs both are taken into consideration. Inflow of the foreign capital through FIIs route termed as hot money which brings foreign currency (\$) into the country and contributes large foreign exchange reserve into the country to enhance the efficiency of the Indian economy. Apart from that large portion of capital in stock market comes through domestic route, in which MFs play a significant role. Thus, the development of capital market depends not only on the foreign capital but also upon the domestic investment route. This study reveals that these two investment routes have low degree of positive correlation between each other whereas FIIs don't make their investment decisions as per the investment scenario of MFs, whereas positive and negative movement of SnX affects the investment decisions of FIIs. Because, FIIs look for income, if the economy grows they enter into the stock market of concerned economy but exit from the market with the same speed as they entered.

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